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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND INVITRO EVALUATION OF
ATOMEXETINE BUCCAL PATCH BY SOLVENT CASTING
METHOD**Karthika^{*1}, N. Sandeepthi,²Nellutla Jhancy Laxmi³¹Holy Mary Institute of Science and Technology(College of Pharmacy) Bogaram(V),Keesara (M) dist-501301²Holy Mary Institute of Science and Technology(College of Pharmacy) Bogaram(V),Keesara (M) dist-501301**Abstract:**

Amongst the various routes of administration tried so far in the novel drug delivery systems, localized drug delivery to tissues of the oral cavity has been investigated for the treatment of periodontal disease, bacterial and fungal infection. Over the decades mucoadhesion has become popular for its potential to optimize localized drug delivery, by retaining a dosage form at the site of action (e.g. within the gastrointestinal tract) or systemic delivery by retaining the formulation in intimate contact with the absorption site (e.g. buccal cavity.) [1] Well defined bioadhesion is the ability of a material (synthetic or biological) to adhere to a biological tissue for an extended period of time. The biological surface can be epithelial tissue or it can be the mucus coat on the surface of a tissue. If adhesion is to a mucous coat, the phenomenon is referred to as mucoadhesion.

KEY WORDS: Mucoadhesion , Buccal cavity , gastrointestinal tract

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INTRODUCTION:

A "holy grail" of treatment options for attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) has been an agent with low abuse potential and peak-trough clinical effects, providing sustained therapeutic benefits throughout the day. Atomoxetine is the first non-stimulant drug approved for the treatment of attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). It is sold in the form of the hydrochloride salt of atomoxetine. This chemical is manufactured and

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

marketed under the brand name Strattera; by Eli Lilly and Company and as a generic Attentin by Torrent Pharmaceuticals. There is currently no generic available within the United States due to patent restrictions. Atomoxetine is a norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor that selectively inhibits the presynaptic norepinephrine transporter. A growing body of literature supports the use of atomoxetine both in children and adults with ADHD.

TABLE:1

S.NO	Material Name
1	Atomoxetine
2	Ethanol
3	Eudragit L-100
4	HPMCK ₁₅ M
5	HPMCK ₄ M
6	Methanol

TABLE 2: FORMULATIONS OF ATOMOXETINE BUCCAL PATCH

S.No	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
1	Drug(mg)	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
2	Eudragit-L100(mg)	200	250	300	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	150	-
3	HPMCK ₄ M(mg)	-	-	-	200	250	300	-	-	-	150	-	150
4	HPMCK ₁₅ M(mg)	-	-	-	-	-	-	200	250	300	-	150	150
5	Dichloromethane(ml)	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
6	Ethanol(ml)	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
7	Propylene glycol(ml)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
8	Tween-80(ml)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3

RESULTS & DISCUSSION**Standard Calibration curve of Atomoxetine:****Table 3:** Concentration and absorbance obtained for calibration curve of Atomoxetine in(pH 6.8)

S. No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance* (at 271 nm)
1	2	0.128
2	4	0.267
3	6	0.456
4	8	0.589
5	10	0.762
6	12	0.963

It was found that the estimation of Atomoxetine by UV spectrophotometric method at λ_{\max} 271 nm in 0.1N Hydrochloric acid had good reproducibility and this method was used in the study. The correlation coefficient for the standard curve was found to be closer to 1, at the concentration range, 2-10 μ g/ml. The regression equation generated was $y = 0.0636x + 0.0751$.

Fig 1: Standard graph of Atomoxetine in pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer

Evaluation of Atomoxetine Buccal patches :

Physical appearance : All the Buccal patches were visually inspected for colour, clarity, flexibility.

Flatness : All the Buccal patches was found to be flat with out any foams.

Table No. 4 : Evaluation of Buccal patch by physical methods

Formulation	Thickness (mm)	Folding endurance	Drug content (%)	Moisture uptake (%)	Moisture content (%)
F1	0.3569	20	45	7.98	3.77
F2	0.3520	25	65	25.05	9.2
F3	0.3470	27	57.5	13.09	5.16
F4	0.3496	24	60	15.63	5.66
F5	0.3460	30	67.5	11.73	4.87
F6	0.3517	32	92.5	19.65	12.67
F7	0.3478	40	101.7	9.42	3.43
F8	0.3437	37	85	10.87	4.72
F9	0.3503	34	55	16.44	6.62
F10	0.3532	29	62.5	13.08	6.17
F11	0.3546	26	85	20.63	7.94
F12	0.3503	31	82.5	15.73	6.55

The prepared Atomoxetine Buccal patches were evaluated by physical methods such as Physical appearance, Flatness, Weight variation, Thickness, Folding endurance, Drug content, Moisture uptake and Moisture content and all the results were found to be with in the pharmacopeial limits.

Table No. 5: Evaluation of Buccal patch by In-vitro permeation studies using dialysis membrane

Time (hrs)	% Drug release											
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
1	9.05	15.1	10.1	9.49	10.9	20.2	17.5	12.0	11.1	12.7	10.0	20.4
2	13.3	19.8	12.8	11.3	19.6	27.8	21.9	17.5	13.0	17.9	12.5	25.4
4	14.6	28.3	21.5	22.6	24.9	42.8	33.5	23.4	23.3	27.4	23.6	33.0
6	21.9	34.1	25.9	32.3	31.2	53.5	40.0	30.9	33.4	32.7	30.9	41.7
8	32.7	41.1	33.4	43.9	38.0	66.3	46.5	48.1	52.7	50.6	36.7	47.9
10	40.4	50.1	44.5	56.3	50.3	82.0	64.2	60.0	66.4	63.0	45.9	63.0
12	54.2	65.8	56.7	69.4	65.9	94.7	91.9	78.7	79.1	74.8	56	80.9

Fig No. 2 : Release profile of In-vitro permeation studies using dialysis membrane

The prepared Atomoxetine Buccal patches were evaluated for In-vitro permeation studies using dialysis membrane, Among all the 12 formulations F6 formulation which contain HPMC K4M 300mg and Eudragit L-100 60mg had shown 94% cumulative drug release with in 12 hours. And compared to HPMC K15M, HPMC K4M showed better drug release profile.

Table No 6 : kinetics of In-vitro permeation studies using dialysis membrane

Cumulative (%) release Q	Time (T)	Root (T)	Log (%) release	Log (T)	Log (%) remain	Release rate (cumulative % release/t)	1/cum % release	Peppas log Q/100	% drug remain	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
20.2356	1	1.000	1.306	0.000	1.902	20.236	0.0494	-0.694	79.7644	4.642	4.305	0.337
27.80759	2	1.414	1.444	0.301	1.858	13.904	0.0360	-0.556	72.19241	4.642	4.164	0.478
42.87958	4	2.000	1.632	0.602	1.757	10.720	0.0233	-0.368	57.12042	4.642	3.851	0.790
53.59293	6	2.449	1.729	0.778	1.667	8.932	0.0187	-0.271	46.40707	4.462	3.594	1.048
66.38743	8	2.828	1.822	0.903	1.527	8.270	0.0151	-0.178	33.61257	4.642	3.227	1.414
82.0877	10	3.162	1.914	1.000	1.253	8.209	0.0122	-0.086	17.9123	4.642	2.616	2.025
94.7055	12	3.464	1.976	1.079	0.724	7.892	0.0106	-0.024	5.294503	4.642	1.743	2.899

Fig No. 3 : Zero order kinetics

Fig No. 4 : Higuchi plot

Fig No. 5 : Peppas plot

Fig No. 6 : First order kinetics

The kinetics of In-vitro permeation studies using dialysis membrane for F6 formulation was plotted and the Regression coefficient value was found to be high for Korsmeyer-peppas release model i.e., 0.9892. And the n value was found to be 0.6203 which indicates the drug release pattern was found to be non-Fickian diffusion.

